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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Формирование здоровьесберегающей образовательной среды в начальной школе в условиях инклюзии.....	10
Тургунова Нилуфар Абдусаломовна	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tez va aniq hisoblash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari.....	16
Dehqonova Maxliyoxon Shuhratjon, Musinjonova Dildoraxon Mahmudjon	
Научно-педагогический анализ методов математического моделирования: численные и аналитические подходы в обучении студентов.....	19
Мусурмонова Маъмура Оман кизи, Жураева Феруза Бахтиёр кизи, Сарсенбаева Мархабо Шадибековна	
Inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijtimoiy moslashuvini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi.....	26
Turdimurodova Muazzam Muzaffarbek qizi	
M. Tvenning "Tom Soyerning boshidan kechirganlari" romanida bolalar obrazining tasviri masalasi.....	29
Sattarov Farrux Nuridinovich	
Pedagogik dasturiy vositalar yordamida dars sifatini oshirish.....	35
D. K. Ibadullayev	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning kasbga qiziqishlarini rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik zaruriyati.....	41
Isabekova Dilafruz Shermirzayevna	
Молодёжь Узбекистана в системе политических процессов.....	46
Юсупова Элеонора Фердинандовна	
Matematika o'qitishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar: vaziyatli tahlil va amaliy samaradorlik.....	51
Matyaqubova Nazira Hikmat qizi	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning pedagogik mahoratini sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari asosida rivojlantirishning metodik modeli.....	54
Choriyev Olmosbek Baxriddin o'g'li	
Fan va tilni integratsiyalashgan holda o'qitish (CLIL).....	60
M. D. Boynazarova	
Оптимизация показателей сердечного цикла у спортсменов при хроническом физическом перенапряжении посредством фармакологической поддержки.....	63
Нормуратов Абдулла Саппарович	
Chidamlilikka yo'naltirilgan sport turlarida uglevod va energiya almashinuvini farmakologik korreksiyasi....	67
Normuratov Abdulla Sapparovich	
O'quvchilarga dutor ijrochiligini o'rgatishning pedagogik yondashuvlari.....	70
Sa'dullayev Og'abek Abdurashid o'g'li, Nazirullayeva Nodira Akmal qizi	
Bolalar musiqa va san'at maktablarida individual va jamoa mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish mexanizmlari (cholg'u ijrochiligi misolida).....	74
Omonova Charos Baxodir qizi	
Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachilarining o'quv-biluv faoliyatini motivatsiyalashda interfaol metodlardan foydalanish.....	79
Saidova Zulfizar Norbobo qizi	
O'qituvchining kognitiv egizagi (Digital Twin): sun'iy intellekt yordamida individual pedagogik uslubni modellashtirish.....	83
Kuchkarova Feruza Qambaraliyevna	
Abdusamad Boboxo'jayev rahbarligida tarix va arxeologiya institutining rivoji: 1964-yilgi arxiv hujjati misolida.....	91
Abdullayev Botir Jabbor o'g'li	
Maktab o'quvchilarining musiqiy idrokni shakllantirishning ijtimoiy va didaktik zarurati.....	93
Abdumannan Maxammatov	

“Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida kalokagatiyani rivojlantirishning KAMOL modeli asosidagi pedagogik texnologiyasi”	97
<i>Abdurahmonova Dilorom Jovliyevna</i>	
Morphological Structure and Word Formation of Ecotourism Terminology: A Cross-Linguistic Analysis With Reference to the Uzbek Language.....	104
<i>Absamatova Charos</i>	
Fizika fanini o'tmda o'qitishda masalalar yechishning ilmiy-metodik ahamiyati	107
<i>Akmal Mustafoyev Isaqulovich, Munajat Mustafoyeva Oltibekovna</i>	
Kasbiy yo'naltirilgan ingliz tili darslarida metakognitiv strategiyalar asosida akademik nutqni rivojlantirish ..	111
<i>Allamuratov G'ofur Ashurovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda bolalarning mayda qo'l motorikasini rivojlantirish metodikasi	116
<i>Amanova Albina Dexqon qizi</i>	
Psychological Approaches in Teaching English in Preschool Education and their Effectiveness	120
<i>Berdiqulova Zamira Albertovna</i>	
The Role of Family, Education, and Community Systems in Shaping Individual Psychological Well-Being .	124
<i>Diibar Abdullayeva Ubaydullayevna, Iroda Panjiyeva Khayitovna</i>	
Nomoddiy madaniy merosning talaba-yoshlarni yuksak ma'naviyatli shaxs sifatida tarbiyalashdagi ahamiyati	127
<i>Erboyev Suxrob Abdusalomovich</i>	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida inson resurslarini boshqarishda muvozanatlashgan ko'rsatkichlar tizimidan foydalanishning nazariy asoslari	131
<i>Gulmira Jumanova</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini o'stirishda badiiy adabiyotning dolzarbligi	135
<i>Hasanova X. Z.</i>	
Gospital ta'lim sharoitida ona tili fanini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish samaradorligi	139
<i>Hikmatov Bobobek Saydulloyevich</i>	
ASB bo'lgan bolalarda sensor buzilishlarning kognitiv va ijtimoiy rivojlanishga ta'siri	142
<i>Isaxanova Oybarchin Abduraxim qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda kommunikativ faoliyat samaradorligining pedagogik mexanizmlari	146
<i>Maxmutazimova Yulduz Raxmatovna</i>	
David haykali ko'z bo'lagining qalamtasvirini bajarish usullari.....	149
<i>Mo'minov Baxtiyor Karamatovich</i>	
Ta'limda fanlararo integratsiyadan foydalanishning pedagogik va psixologik asoslari	154
<i>Oblakulova Nodira Abduvali qizi</i>	
Ellipslarni tasviriy san'at va muhandislik grafikasida yasash metodikasi.....	160
<i>Sheraliyev Sanjarbek Karimberdiyevich</i>	
Kommunikativ strategiyaning yuzaga kelish omillari	170
<i>Normaxmatova Feruza Ruziboyevna</i>	
Umumta'lim maktab musiqa madaniyati darslarida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish muammo va yechimlari	174
<i>O'rishboyeva Xumora O'rol qizi</i>	
Maktabda jismoniy tarbiya darslarida futbol elementlaridan foydalanib 10-11 yoshli bolalarda tezkor-kuch qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish uslubiyati	177
<i>Qurbonbayeva Maftuna G'ayrat qizi</i>	
Maktabda darsdan tashqari futbol to'garaklarida o'quvchilarning tezkor-kuch qobiliyatlarini takomillashtirish	182
<i>Ro'ziboyeva Fotima Quدرات qizi</i>	
Matn ustida ishlash samaradorligini baholash mezonlari	187
<i>Sadarova Nilufar</i>	
Neyroestetik stimulning yosh dinamikasidagi roli: kognitiv emotsional sferani qayta tashkil etish mexanizmlari.....	193
<i>Salaxidinova Xolida Xaliljonovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	<p>Kasbiy ta'limda o'quvchilarning psixologik va axloqiy sifatlari 198 Salomov Abdurasul Axmadovich</p> <p>Funksiyaning hosilasi yordamida o'sish va kamayish oraliqlarini aniqlash metodikasi 201 Sherzad Eshjanovich Bekchanov, Shohida Sadullaeva Ziyadullaeva, Abdusalom A. Xudoyberdiev</p> <p>Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning kommunikativ qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda psixologik treninglarning nazariy va amaliy asoslari..... 205 Sojida Safarova Saxadin qizi</p> <p>Destruktiv xulq-atvor psixologik va pedagogik qarovsizlik oqibati sifatida..... 207 Umirzoqova Shodiya Lutfullo qizi</p> <p>Maktabgacha ta'limda bolalar bilan innovatsion texnologiyalar yordamida ekologik omillarni singdirish 210 Xoldorova Mashxura G'ulomovna</p> <p>Роль антиоксидантной системы в повышении работоспособности спортсменов 214 Нурбаев Бахтиёр Шириневич</p> <p>Shaxs irodaviy sohasini rivojlantirishning psixologik determinantlari..... 217 To'ychiyeva Shoyista Jumabayevna</p> <p>Ta'lim jarayonida va talabalarning mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning ahamiyati 223 X. Xalilova, N. Niyazova</p> <p>Optimization of Periodontal Disease Treatment Tactics in Patients With Chronic Hepatitis C After Achieving a Sustained Virological Response 227 Makhmudova Ugiloy Bakhtiyorovna</p> <p>Pathogenetic and Clinical Rationale for the Prevention and Management of Periodontal Diseases in Workers Within Dust-Hazardous Environments 230 Turumova Marjona Bakhodirovna</p> <p>Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti direktorlarining boshqaruv faoliyati va kasbiy madaniyati 233 Imamova Nilufar Zabiylxulla qizi, Soloyeva Rayhonoy Ravshanbek qizi</p> <p>Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalarida integratsiyalashgan ijodiy muhitni tashkil etishning ilmiy-metodologik asoslari 236 Sultanov Xaytboy Eraliyevich</p> <p>Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy faoliyat orqali o'smirlarda huquqbuzarlik profilaktikasining pedagogik asoslari 241 Umarov Qobiljon</p> <p>Maktab o'quvchilari orasida kiberbulling profilaktikasi yo'llari 245 Jannazarova Juldizxan Aliiyar qizi</p> <p>Kimyo ta'limi jarayonida kreativ yondashuv asosida kompetensiyaviy yondashuvni rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish 250 Allaberdiyeva Zebinisobegim Ismoiljon qizi</p> <p>Universality in Phraseological Units in English, Dutch and Uzbek 253 Khaydarova Guzalkhon</p> <p>Texnologik ta'limda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning o'quv samaradorligiga ta'siri: universitet darajasida istiqbollor 256 Musurmonova Ma'mura Oman qizi, Berdiyeva Gulnoza Rizoqulovna</p> <p>Chet el va mahalliy tajribalarda muhandislik musobaqalari samaradorligi 261 N. Nomozova, A. Muxamadiyev</p> <p>Autizm spektri buzilishlarining klinik-pedagogik xususiyatlari va ularni korreksiyalashning ilmiy asoslari..... 267 Polatova P. M., Polvonova Kishchan Ravshanovna</p> <p>Tenglamalar ildizlarini aniqlashda vatarlar usuli va python dasturiy modeli 272 Rizayeva Bahoroy Jahongir qizi</p> <p>Algebra fanini o'rganishda talabaning xatolarini tahlil qilish va ularni bartaraf etish usullari 277 Zaxiriddinova Shahlo Zahiriddin qizi, Norboyeva E'zoza O'tabek qizi, Oqbutayeva Sumbula Normuhammad qizi</p> <p>Интегрированный подход как основа развития русской связной речи иноязычных студентов неязыковых специальностей 280 Бозорова Хулкар Одинакуловна</p>
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Оптимизация трудовых отношений в системе общего среднего образования на основе HR-менеджмента: эмпирический анализ.....	284
Турикова Лазокат Машрабовна	
Pedagoglarning huquqiy maqomi hamda global kompetensiyalar bilan bog'liq muammo va yechimlar.....	296
Javohir Baxtiyorovich Shukurov	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida og'zaki nutqni rivojlantirishning kommunikativ yondashuv asoslari.....	305
Holikulova Feruza Xasanovna	
Talabalarda internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanishning agressiv xulq-atvorga ta'siri.....	309
Tosheva Sayyora Raxmonqulovna	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	314
Nurmatova Iroda Toxtasinovna, Qutlimuratova Dilnoza Oybek qizi	
O'quv materiallarini didaktik prinsiplar asosida bayon qilishning nazariy-amaliy asoslari.....	318
Turdiyeva Navruza Sheraliyevna	
Raqamli va globallashtirilgan muhitda maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy qadriyatlarini rivojlantirish.....	323
Avazova Xidoyat Zafar qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish darslarida badiiy asar tahlil qilish kompetensiyasini shakllantirish orqali o'quvchilar nutqini boyitish ("Bog'bon va nihol" rivoyati misolida).....	327
Normurodova Nigora Abdusattorovna, Abduxalilova Mohinur To'raqul qizi	
Qoraqalpog'iston cho'l yaylovlarning holatiga katta qumsichqonlar ta'sirini baholash.....	331
Adilbayeva Genjexan	
O'zbekiston zaminida uyg'onish - renessans hodisasining yuz berishi: shakllanishi, musulmon va insoniyat dunyosi taraqqiyotidagi o'rni.....	335
Choriyev Mirjalol Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Bo'lajak tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarining ekologik kompetentligini badiiy-loyihaviy faoliyat orqali rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	340
Istamov Zavqiddin Sa'dulloevich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida fonetik kompetensiyani rivojlantirish orqali orfoqrafik va orfoepik bilimlarni shakllantirish.....	344
Mamasidikova Naima Toxirjon qizi	
Talabalarining mustaqil o'qish va o'rganish kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning metakognitiv aspektlari.....	348
Mirsobitova Parvina Bahodir qizi	
Sun'iy intellekt vositasida talabalarining axloqiy-estetik madaniyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari..	351
Muminov Zokir Sharop o'g'li	
Ta'lim muhitining o'quvchilarning emotsional holatiga ta'siri.....	354
Nurmatov Nurhayot Nurziyat o'g'li, Otaqurbonbova Nigina Rustam qizi	
STEAM yondashuvi asosida o'simliklar fiziologiyasi fanida o'quv mazmunini didaktik qayta tashkil etish xususiyatlari.....	358
Xoliqulova Gulchehra Alimardon qizi	
Особенности развития эмоционального интеллекта у детей дошкольного возраста.....	363
Мирзаева Наргиза	
Inklyuziv ta'limni tashkil etishning pedagogik asoslari.....	367
Abdanbekova Nilufar Rixsiyevna	
O'qituvchining pedagogik mahoratini takomillashtirish va uni rivojlantirish omillari.....	370
Ismailova Shaira Ferdausovna	
Maktab o'quvchilarida o'zini o'zi tarbiyalashni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari (8–9-sinflar asosida)..	373
Norxo'jayeva Lobar Nuriddin qizi	
Inkluziv ta'limda pedagoglarning mahorati va pedagogik innovatsiyalar.....	378
Raxmonova Gullola Shavkatovna	
The Impact of Collaborative Writing Activities on EFL University Students' Essay Writing Skills: A Classroom-Based Study.....	382
Shovkiewa Munisa Shonazar kizi	

ChatGPT va generativ AI vositalarining o'quv jarayonidagi didaktik imkoniyatlari.....	386
<i>Sotivoldiyev Shohruhmirzo Abdumalik o'g'li</i>	
O'qituvchi shaxsining pedagogik etikasi va kasbiy madaniyati.....	390
<i>Sultonova Nargiza Nigmatovna</i>	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida talabalarning media savodxonligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik mexanizmlari.....	393
<i>Zaxiriddinova Shaxlo, Nurova Manzura, Murodova Fayoza</i>	
Talabalar matematik tafakkurini rivojlantirishda analizdan masalalar yechish strategiyalari	397
<i>Zaxiriddinova Shaxlo, Tuffiyeva Roziya, Ismatullayev Javohir</i>	
Роль социальной компетенции в процессе интенсивного когнитивного развития	402
<i>З. Ф. Азизова</i>	
Роль научного знания в повышении качества образования	406
<i>Сагатова Диёра Абдулазиз кизи</i>	
Методы использование информационных технологий в научном исследовании качества образования в ВУЗе.....	409
<i>Уразова Марина Батыровна, Туленова Карима Жандаровна, Генжебаева Кундуз Саламат кызи</i>	
Академический стресс и формирование механизма “самообвинения” у студентов.....	412
<i>Хошимова Дилорам Анваровна, Немаджанова Наргиза</i>	
OTM, mahalla va oilalarda barqaror ma'naviy-axloqiy muhitni takomillashtirish tizimi.....	416
<i>Karshiyev Jaxongir Abdirayimovich, Abdilaxatov Zafar Abdigapirovich</i>	
O'smirlar deviant xulq-atvori shakllanishida ijtimoiy tarmoqlarga qaramlik bosh omil sifatida.....	421
<i>Olliberdiyeva Buoysha Baxromjon qizi, Tohirova Go'zaloy Davronbek qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'limda tasviriy va amaliy san'at integratsiyasining zamonaviy pedagogik metodlari (Buxoro amaliy san'ati misolida).....	426
<i>Abdullayev Suxrob Sayfullayevich</i>	
STEAM texnologiyalari va uning qo'llanilishi	431
<i>Atenov Jandarbek Dayrabay o'g'li</i>	
Deviant xulq shakllanishining biopsixologik faktorlari.....	435
<i>Ro'ziqulova Sevinch Ubaydullo qizi, Tohirova Go'zal Davronbek qizi</i>	
Эмоциональная устойчивость как психологический фактор развития профессиональной компетентности будущих педагогов	438
<i>Рафиев Фарход Акилович</i>	
Pedagog kadrlarni innovatsion faoliyatga tayyorlashni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirishning metod va mexanizmlari.....	441
<i>Aziboyev Shuhrat Olimovich</i>	
Bola nutqi buzilishlarining psixologik sabablari.....	445
<i>Xadicha Kamalova, Ziyodullo Elov</i>	
O'quvchilarda kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirish orqali tanqidiy fikrlash va mustaqil o'qish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	449
<i>Xolmatova Sabohat Ilhomovna</i>	
O'qish savodxonligi darslarida xalqaro baholash tadqiqoti topshiriqlaridan foydalanish	453
<i>Boychayeva Sharifa Saidkulovna</i>	
Формирование иноязычной коммуникативной компетенции с помощью задания “диктоглосс”	458
<i>Касымова Феруза Суннатовна</i>	
Ta'lim paradigmalarining evolyutsiyasi va zamonaviy tendensiyalari	463
<i>Abdug'aniyeva Shaxzoda Shuxrat qizi</i>	
O'qish savodxonligi darslarida badiiy va ilmiy-ommabop matnlardan foydalanishning didaktik imkoniyatlari	467
<i>Ostonova Madina Furqat qizi</i>	
Milliy cholg'u sozlar va ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	471
<i>Raimjonov Sunnatulla O'ktamovich</i>	
Forsayt pedagogikasi asosida talabalarning kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning amaliy jihatlari	475
<i>Dushaboyeva Dinara Bahrom qizi</i>	

Sun'iy intellekt yordamida individual o'qish yo'nalishini yaratish	479
<i>Irgasheva Madina Irgashovna</i>	
Ahmad al-Farg'oniyning hayot yo'li va ilm-fanga qo'shgan hissasi	484
<i>Temirov Nabijon Solievich, Mo'sajonova Gulxumor Abduhalim qizi</i>	
Data-Driven yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanishini monitoring qilish va prognozlash modeli	487
<i>Valiyev Jasurbek Saydullo o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini inklyuziv ta'lim berishga tayyorlash mexanizmlari	491
<i>Axmedova Orzigul Tulqinovna</i>	
Mustaqil ish – ta'lim sifatini oshirish mezonidir	498
<i>Erkayev Elmirza Temirovich</i>	
Kasbiy tayyorgarlik jarayonida talabalarda kreativlikni rivojlantirishning psixologik shartlari.....	503
<i>Qobulov O'mirbek Azamat o'g'li</i>	
Kiberbullin onlyn tahdid va uning o'smir xulq-atvoriga ta'siri	509
<i>Saloxiddinova Xumora Mamamrayim qizi, Tohirova Go'zaloy Davronbek qizi</i>	
Yosh voleybolchi qizlarning muvozanat saqlash qobiliyatini oshirish	514
<i>Saparboyeva Muhayyo Farhod qizi</i>	
Talabalarda kasbiy kreativ kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishni psixologik pedagogik jihatlari.....	517
<i>Tohirova Go'zaloy Davronbek qizi, Sharipova Feruza Xo'jamurod qizi</i>	
O'quv bilish faolligi tushunchasining pedagogik-psixologik mohiyati.....	520
<i>Sattarova Gulinoza Salim qizi</i>	
Voleybol sport turini o'rgatish va uning mohiyati.....	523
<i>Turg'unov Baxtiyor O'rolovich</i>	
Malakali sportchilarni texnik tayyorgarligiga zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish yo'llari	526
<i>Eryigitov Dilshod Xolboyevich</i>	
Digitalization as a Driver of Inclusive Education: Enhancing Accessibility, Equity, and Learning Outcomes	529
<i>Muhabbat Nazaraliyevna Toshmurodova</i>	
Digital Transformation of HRM in Higher Education: Evidence from Uzbekistan	534
<i>D. Umirova</i>	

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF HRM IN HIGHER EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Digital technologies are transforming HRM in higher education, enhancing institutional efficiency. This study analyzes the state and challenges of digital HRM in Uzbekistan, including infrastructure gaps, lack of HR analytics, limited competencies, and resistance to change. An integrated model is proposed, emphasizing the importance of leadership and alignment with labor market demands.

Key words: digital transformation, human resource management, higher education, digital HR, HR analytics, institutional performance.

Annotatsiya: Raqamli texnologiyalar oliy ta'limda kadrlar boshqaruvini tubdan o'zgartirmoqda va institutsional samaradorlikni oshirishda muhim omilga aylanmoqda. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda HRMning raqamli transformatsiyasi holati va asosiy muammolari (infrastructure, HR-analitika, kompetensiyalar, qarshilik) tahlil qilinadi. Integratsiyalashgan model taklif etilib, muvaffaqiyatli transformatsiya texnologiya bilan birga rahbarlik va bozor bilan uyg'unlikni talab qilishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli transformatsiya, kadrlar boshqaruvi, oliy ta'lim, digital HR, HR-analitika, institutsional samaradorlik.

Аннотация: Цифровые технологии трансформируют управление персоналом в высшем образовании, повышая институциональную эффективность. В статье анализируются состояние и проблемы цифровой трансформации HRM в Узбекистане (инфраструктура, HR-аналитика, компетенции, сопротивление изменениям). Предложена интегрированная модель, подчеркивающая роль управления и соответствия требованиям рынка труда.

Ключевые слова: цифровая трансформация, управление персоналом, высшее образование, цифровой HR, HR-аналитика, институциональная эффективность.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of digital technologies has significantly reshaped higher education, emphasizing the growing importance of effective human resource management (HRM). In a knowledge-based economy, universities are expected to enhance innovation, human capital development, and responsiveness to labor market demands. Consequently, institutional performance increasingly depends on the strategic management of academic and administrative staff. Traditionally, HRM in higher education has been characterized by administrative rigidity and weak integration with institutional strategy. However, digital transformation is redefining HR processes through the use of artificial intelligence, data analytics, and digital platforms, making them more efficient and data-driven. In developed countries, digital HR systems such as e-recruitment, performance analytics, and online learning environments have already improved decision-making and human capital utilization.

In Uzbekistan, despite ongoing reforms aimed at digitalization and internationalization, the transformation of HRM remains at an early stage. Key challenges include limited digital infrastructure, insufficient use of HR analytics, low digital competencies among staff, and resistance to organizational change. These issues are further intensified by fragmented reform efforts and the lack of an integrated strategic approach.

Although existing studies highlight the role of human capital and digitalization, comprehensive research on digital HRM in higher education remains limited. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the current state and challenges of digital HRM and to propose an integrated model that combines technological, organizational, and strategic dimensions. The research adopts a systemic perspective, emphasizing that successful digital transformation requires not only technological adoption but also effective leadership, institutional autonomy, and alignment with labor market needs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of digital transformation in human resource management (HRM) is grounded in the theories of strategic HRM, human capital development, and knowledge-based organizations. Traditional HRM focuses on aligning human resources with organizational goals through recruitment, training, and performance management; however, digital technologies have significantly expanded these functions. Modern HRM increasingly relies on digital tools and data analytics to enhance efficiency and support strategic decision-making. In knowledge-intensive sectors such as higher education, this shift is particularly important, as institutions depend on the continuous development of academic competencies and effective knowledge management.

Digital transformation in higher education reflects broader global changes driven by technological innovation and increasing competition. It involves the adoption of digital tools such as e-recruitment systems, learning management platforms, and performance analytics, which improve transparency and enable data-driven decision-making. International studies emphasize that these innovations can significantly enhance institutional efficiency; however, their successful implementation requires not only technological infrastructure but also organizational change, leadership support, and the development of digital competencies.

A key element of digital HRM is the use of HR analytics, which allows institutions to collect and interpret data on staff performance and development. Data-driven approaches improve strategic planning and organizational outcomes, although their application in developing contexts remains limited due to technical and institutional constraints. In Uzbekistan, existing research highlights the importance of human capital, digitalization, and alignment with labor market demands, yet comprehensive studies integrating digital HRM within higher education are still insufficiently developed. Overall, the literature indicates that while digital transformation offers significant opportunities for improving HRM systems, there remains a clear research gap in developing integrated frameworks that link digital HR practices with institutional performance, particularly in the context of Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative-analytical research design complemented by comparative and conceptual approaches to examine the digital transformation of human resource management (HRM) in higher education. Given the multi-dimensional nature of digital HRM, encompassing technological, organizational, and strategic components, a qualitative approach enables an in-depth interpretation of institutional practices, policy frameworks, and theoretical perspectives. Comparative analysis facilitates the identification of gaps between international best practices and the current situation in Uzbekistan, while conceptual modeling supports the development of an integrated digital HRM framework. The research is based on the integration of primary and secondary data sources, including national policy documents, regulatory frameworks, international reports, and academic literature.

Analytical methods such as system analysis, content analysis, and logical synthesis are applied to examine HRM as an interconnected system and to extract key patterns related to digital transformation. The conceptual framework is structured around the relationship between digital HRM, academic staff competencies, and institutional performance, emphasizing the role of digital tools such as e-recruitment, HR analytics, and data-driven decision-making, as well as moderating factors including leadership, institutional autonomy, and digital infrastructure.

The study follows a structured research procedure, including literature review, data collection, analytical processing, model development, and interpretation of findings. To ensure reliability and validity, the research applies data triangulation, established theoretical frameworks, and consistent analytical techniques. However, the study is limited by its qualitative nature and the lack of extensive empirical data, indicating the need for further validation of the proposed model in future research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of digital human resource management (HRM) in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan reveals a set of interconnected structural, functional, technological, and organizational challenges, indicating that digitalization remains fragmented and insufficiently integrated into institutional systems. Centralized governance structures continue to limit flexibility in decision-making and hinder the adoption of digital HR tools, while HR departments are largely confined to administrative roles rather than strategic functions. Functional inefficiencies persist in recruitment, performance evaluation, and professional development processes, which remain predominantly traditional and weakly aligned with competency-based and digital approaches.

Technological limitations further constrain transformation, as many institutions lack integrated digital infrastructure and effective use of HR analytics, while staff digital competencies remain underdeveloped. Organizational and cultural barriers, including resistance to change and limited leadership support, also slow down the adoption of digital practices. In addition, a significant misalignment exists between HRM systems and labor

market demands, resulting in gaps in required competencies. Overall, these challenges are systemic and interdependent, highlighting the need for an integrated approach that combines technological innovation with organizational and strategic reforms to enhance institutional performance.

The findings indicate that digital transformation in human resource management (HRM) within higher education institutions remains fragmented and largely administrative, necessitating a systemic and integrated approach. In response, this study proposes a conceptual model grounded in digital transformation, strategic HRM, and human capital theory, emphasizing that digital HRM should be understood as a comprehensive transformation of processes, organizational culture, and decision-making rather than merely the adoption of technological tools. The model is structured around a causal relationship in which digital HRM practices influence academic staff competencies, which in turn determine institutional performance, forming a dynamic and adaptive system.

The framework integrates key components such as e-recruitment, HR analytics, digital performance management, continuous professional development, and data-driven decision-making, while recognizing the critical role of moderating factors including institutional autonomy, leadership, governance, digital infrastructure, and organizational culture. The implementation of this model is expected to enhance institutional efficiency, improve academic quality, and strengthen alignment with labor market demands. As illustrated in Figure 1, the model highlights the systemic interaction between digital HR tools and organizational outcomes, demonstrating that successful transformation depends on the coordinated interaction of technological, strategic, and institutional factors.

Figure 1: Conceptual model of digital human resource management in higher education

The proposed model, illustrated in Figure 1, demonstrates the systemic relationship between digital HRM practices, academic staff competencies, and institutional performance. It highlights that the successful implementation of digital HR tools leads to the development of key competencies, which in turn enhance institutional effectiveness. The model also emphasizes the critical role of moderating factors such as autonomy, governance, leadership, and digital infrastructure in shaping the outcomes of digital transformation. The findings of this study and the proposed digital human resource management (HRM) model have important implications for policy, institutional governance, academic practice, and future research. At the national level, there is a clear need for a comprehensive policy framework that supports digital HR transformation through the development of standardized HR practices, investment in digital infrastructure, and the promotion of digital competencies among academic and administrative staff. Strengthening institutional autonomy and aligning higher education systems with labor market requirements are also essential for enhancing flexibility, innovation, and the relevance of human capital development.

At the institutional level, universities should transition from administrative HRM to strategic digital HRM by integrating digital platforms, competency-based frameworks, and data-driven decision-making into their management practices. This transformation enhances efficiency, transparency, and staff development while improving evaluation systems and professional growth opportunities. For academic staff, digital HRM promotes competency development, more objective performance assessment, and continuous learning; however, it may also increase workload and require additional support. From a research perspective, the study provides a conceptual foundation for future empirical investigations, particularly in areas such as HR analytics, artificial intelligence, and cross-country comparisons. More broadly, digital HRM contributes to the development of human capital, economic growth, and national competitiveness, underscoring its strategic importance for sustainable development.

CONCLUSION

The digital transformation of human resource management (HRM) is a key driver of modernization in higher education, particularly in the context of ongoing reforms in Uzbekistan. This study demonstrates that, despite initial progress, digital HRM systems remain fragmented and insufficiently integrated into institutional strategies, limiting their overall effectiveness. The findings emphasize that digital transformation extends beyond technological adoption and requires comprehensive organizational change supported by strategic leadership, institutional autonomy, and the development of digital competencies. A central contribution of this research is the proposed integrated model linking digital HR practices with academic staff competencies and institutional performance, highlighting the role of governance and infrastructure as critical moderating factors.

The study also offers practical implications for policymakers and institutional leaders, suggesting that the adoption of digital HR systems, competency-based frameworks, and continuous professional development can significantly enhance institutional performance. However, the research is limited by its qualitative nature and the lack of empirical validation, indicating the need for further studies. Overall, digital HRM transformation should be viewed as a strategic imperative capable of improving educational quality and supporting long-term socio-economic development.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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